

Design of pyridinium luminophore structural and optical properties for tailored sensor response

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia"

(No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "Design of pyridinium luminophore structural and optical properties for tailored sensor response", No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0040.

The project is focused on the design of the structure, chemical, and optical properties of pyridinium luminophore for optical gas sensor applications:

- to design structure, optical, and sensitive properties of pyridinium luminophores by theoretical calculations
- to fabricate pyridinium luminophores from solution with fixed concentration and different drying rates
- to investigate the chemical, structure, and optical properties of the fabricated pyridinium luminophores
- to investigate optical stability and sensor properties towards saturated vapors of model molecules

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Artis Kinens (0000-0003-1992-525X)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Design of pyridinium luminophore structural and optical properties for tailored sensor response

Description:

The Data Management Plan is developed in the framework of the Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia"

(No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant project "Design of pyridinium luminophore structural and optical properties for tailored sensor response", No. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0040.

The project is focused on the design of the structure, chemical, and optical properties of pyridinium luminophore for optical gas sensor applications:

- to design structure, optical, and sensitive properties of pyridinium luminophores by theoretical calculations
- to fabricate pyridinium luminophores from solution with fixed concentration and different drying rates
- to investigate the chemical, structure, and optical properties of the fabricated pyridinium luminophores
- to investigate optical stability and sensor properties towards saturated vapors of model molecules

Researchers:

Artis Kinens (0000-0003-1992-525X)

Organizations:

University of Latvia

Contact: Viter Roman (roman.viter@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: EU Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No. 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project: Design of pyridinium luminophore structural and optical properties for tailored sensor response

3. License

License: CC0-1.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-11-30

4. Templates

Descriptions

Photoluminescence data

Photoluminescence spectra, obtained during optical characterization and sensor testing.

CSV files

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

30

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The data will be used for publications and as reference to compare with other compounds

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

It will be repositied on onedrive as csv files.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Access will be provided by request after publishing the data

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Embargo before publication

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Internet browser and Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Academic Free License 3.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-03-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-03-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Roman Viter 0000-0002-9996-041X

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Structure characterization data

FTIR and XRD spectra will be added to the project data repository

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

30

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

This is a new data

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

XRD, FTIR

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Access upon request

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Before publishing the data

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Internet Browser, Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Academic Free License 3.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-03-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2027-03-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Roman Viter 0000-0002-9996-041X

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

